

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE USE OF EXPERIENCE OF THE KOREAN PRESCHOOL SYSTEM IN PREPARATORY GROUPS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Obidova Nargiza Saibjonovna
Andijan State Pedagogical Institute,
Master of the Department of preschool education
E-mail: Obidovanargiza744@gmail.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7956115>

ANNOTATION: The article presents the content, means, methods and methods of the educational process in preschool educational institutions, the results of a study of the Korean preschool education system from a scientific and pedagogical point of view.

Key words: education, process, content, means, organization, methods and methods, Korea, preschool education system.

Introduction: One of our important tasks is to bring up the young generation growing in our country over the past period as healthy and mature in every way, to introduce effective forms and methods into the educational process and to organize an effective system of preschool education aimed at promoting innovative ideas. At the same time, the analysis carried out shows the need to ensure the coverage of children with preschool education, fill organizations with educational and methodological materials and fiction, attract qualified pedagogical and managerial personnel to the field, and solve the issues of introducing innovative technologies in the educational process. The effective implementation of these tasks places a tremendous responsibility on the responsibility of educators, stylists and psychologists operating in preschool educational organizations.

Everyone is aware that a number of decrees, decrees and decrees adopted by our state in this regard are aimed at a radical reform of the preschool education system [1-4].

The provision of modern education to children from preschool age, their active development psychically, mentally and socially-is one of the current issues that should be solved in preschool educational organizations.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY: In the education system of developed countries, a number of terms have been widely used in recent years. These include the concepts of tyutor, edweiser, facilitator and moderator.

Today, human society, as well as finding a solution to the socio-economic, ideological-political, educational-educational problems facing the people of our independent republic, depends on the interaction and interaction of natural, social, technical sciences. Because, all of them, according to their essence, content, nature, form and scope, have a systemic character, which is studied and solved using exactly the appropriate approach to them. This in turn provides for the use of a systematic approach in educational work as well. Well-known Russian psychological scientist G.S. In Kostyuk's view: "while differentiation leads to an increase in differentiation – mental processes and states (traits), integration - regulation leads to subordination and the placement of its results in a given sequence. By integration, a new psychological process, a new structure of activity is formed. This new structure is generated

by synthesis from previously isolated elements". Genetically, integration is the form and higher level of logically completed content, synthesizing the content of educational subjects at least at the level of educational standards, complementing, expanding and deepening continuity, interdependence, interplay, and finally mutually complementary. Because any lower level of interdisciplinarity, established among certain didactic units within the framework of the subjects of study under study, provides for the Coordination of the content and deadlines for their study, in contrast to the educational subject organized on the basis of integrative communication, or integrating the subject, phenomenon or processes under study in the form of a holistic system, requires

Within the framework of the state visit of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Republic of Korea, about 20 meetings were held by the Ministry of preschool education, agreements were reached to exchange experiences, open kindergartens in Uzbekistan in an experimental way, study the possibilities of Joint Staff Training and scientific research.

Within the framework of the trip, the Ministry of preschool education of the Republic of Uzbekistan organized visits to a number of Korean preschool and other types of institutions and studied their activities, including the specifics of kindergartens, the methods of teaching used, financing and payment systems, the level of qualifications and conditions of service of pedagogical staff, food and material and technical

The creation of maximum favorable conditions for the activities of educators, the creative freedom of the educator, the absence of large-scale reports, the high social status of Educators of State kindergartens, the creative environment created for children to manifest themselves, including the comfortable design and equipment of rooms to even small details, the availability of rich literature and developmental games for them, from early childhood, special aspects such as behavior in society and the upbringing of personal hygiene skills form the basis of the success of the Korean preschool education system.

Another aspect to pay special attention is that the state provides care to the most unprotected segments of society, low-income families and children with disabilities, first and foremost, and applies the principle of priority to kindergartens during admission, and therefore, the principles of inclusive education in Korea are admirable [5, 6].

Hadli agreements were signed with Sanmyong University, (Sangmyung University) and Chung-Ang University (ChungAng University) in order to promote cooperation with higher education institutions specializing in the training of personnel to the Korean educational system and under the jurisdiction of preschool institutions, as well as memorandum of cooperation with Chonnam National University (Chonnam National University).

The experience of the Republic of Korea is definitely noteworthy and we believe that the elements of the Korean model in this regard will definitely be reflected in the processes of reforming the preschool education system in Uzbekistan.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS: It is darcor that the NA'anana activities, festive events and precepts conducted will be colorful, interesting, have a projected technological map of the previously carefully thought - out training. In what way or form to draw up a technological map of training, it directly depends on the experience, the purpose and creativity of the educator. Drawing up a technological map will save the educator from writing an extended synopsis of training, since on such a map all aspects of the training process are reflected.

In the experimental groups, it was found that the number of high-level responses to assignments in academic year training increased by 7.1% compared to control groups, the number of mid-level responses increased by 4.2%, and the number of lower-level responses decreased by 10.2%.

Table 1.

The worldview of preschool children at the beginning of the experiment degree of formation.

Groups	Number of educators	Answers					
		At the beginning of the school year			At the end of the academic year		
		HL	ML	LL	HL	ML	LL
Experience	98	27/27,5	36/36,7	35/35,8	45/46	47/48	6/6
Control	94	28/29,8	31/33	35/37,2	36/38,3	41/43,6	17/18,1

Note: HL – high level; ML – middle level; LL – lower level; percentage in denominator

In our research, we used the criterion χ^2 (xi-square), one of the criteria for mathematical statistical methods of pedagogical research, to determine the effectiveness of didactic materials and recommendations proposed, the reliability of the results obtained from the pedagogical experiment carried out.

Since the work studied by US is measured on a scale of grades above two categories, that is, the assimilated concepts of educators are measured in HL, ML, LL, the calculations were carried out according to the following formula:

$$T_{кыз} = \frac{1}{n_1 \cdot n_2} \sum_{i=1}^c \frac{(n_1 Q_{2i} - n_2 Q_{1i})^2}{Q_{1i} + Q_{2i}}$$

In this:

T_{kuz} – statistical criterion observation value

C – number of categories

$v = 1, 2, 3$ – category number

$\alpha = 0,05$ – pre-given degree of importance

n_1, n_2 – number of objects under study (number of subjects of control and experiment group)

Q_{1i} – the number of first-choice objects per category I (grade) in terms of the nature of the study (we have the number of students of the experimental class who received a certain grade)

Q_{2i} – the number of second-choice objects per category I (grade) in terms of the nature of the study (we have the number of control class students who have received a certain grade)

Before making calculations, we put forward the following assumptions. If $\alpha = 0.05$, the values obtained by the calculations, that is, the observational value of the statistical criterion (T_{kuz}) from the critical value of the statistical criterion (T_{krit}) when large ($T_{kuz} > T_{krit}$), in it, the H_0 conjecture is negated and the H_1 conjecture is accepted. If ($T_{kuz} < T_{krit}$) assuming H_0 is assumed.

Given that the degrees of freedom in US are $v = 2, 3, 4$ and the degree of importance is $\alpha = 0.05$, T_{krit} we define. Its value was found to be 5,991, respectively, in accordance with the degrees of freedom given.

Based on the results of the experimental work carried out, computer calculations were carried out using a program developed for the χ^2 criterion and compared with T_{krit} values.

1- for the table $T_{kuz} = 6,523 > T_{krit} = 5,991$

According to the results $T_{kuz} > T_{krit}$, which means that the H_0 conjecture is negated and the H_1 conjecture is acceptable.

Taking into account the statistical significance of the values obtained as a result of Formula-based calculations, the effectiveness of our research work and the proposed materials and recommendations was confirmed from a pedagogical point of view.

Conclusions And Suggestions:

"The content, means of the educational process, methods and methods of its organization. We have come to the following conclusions on the research work on the topic" preschool education system in Korea:

1. Theoretical and practical concepts studied and analyzed indicate that the pedagogical foundations of the formation of the worldview of preschool children, effective approaches based on the extinction of modern methods of the Korean educational system, the development of tools and methods are one of the pressing problems of today's turbulent period.

2. The fact that the formation of the worldview of preschool children should be carried out directly taking into account their age and psychological characteristics was also manifested in the analysis of the studied psychological literature. That is, the need for the participation of all psychic processes in this: intuition, perception, attention, memory, thinking, speech, was analyzed according to the recognition of psychologist scientists.

3. The result of the observation work and conversations carried out shows that the main tool for growing children's worldview in Mtms is Toys. Through toys, children in the process of their activities show their attitude towards the environment, people.

4. The results obtained showed the need to consistently work with children on growing their worldview, not only in Mtms, but also in families, extracurricular educational institutions.

5. It was found that the main focus in raising children's worldview should be on travel activities that are organized with them. Because it is during travel activities that children's interest and attitude towards the environment are formed.

6. It was found that the use of innovative technologies, creative techniques in the process of training is an important factor in the formation of a children's worldview.

7. Taking into account the importance of exhibitionism in the formation of a children's worldview, the fact that the need to equip each MTM in our republic with multimedia tools was manifested in the process of experimental testing.

All the activities and fairy-tale, festive events that we have conducted, are proposed to organize, will lead to an increase in children's worldview, creativity, thinking. These are poems, Songs, Proverbs, riddles and travel lessons memorized thanks to activities and activities, which, in addition to the formation of future qualities of perfection in children, educate patriotism, nobility, build self-confidence and duty, help to bring the intellectual abilities of students to the surface.

References:

- 1.Mirziyoyev Sh. M. "Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimi boshqaruvini tubdan takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida". 2017-yil 30-sentyabr, 5198-son farmoni.
- 2.O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "O'zbekiston Respublikasi maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasi" 2019 yil 8 maydagi PQ-4312-son qarori
- 3.Ilk va maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar rivojlanishiga qo'yiladigan Davlat talablari. T.: 2018.
- 4."Ilk kadam" maktabgacha ta'lim muassasasining Davlat o'quv dasturi. T.: 2018.
- 5.Ishmuhamedov R.J, Abduqodirov A., Pardaev A. Tarbiyada innovatsion texnologiyalar (ta'lim muassasalari o'qituvchilari, tarbiyachilari, guruh rahbarlari uchun amaliy tavsiyalar). T.: Iste'dod, 2010.
- 6.www.ziyonet.uz.